

NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS

Internally Generated Revenue At State Level

(Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The National Bureau of Statistics Published Internally Generated Revenue at State level for Fourth Quarter and Full Year 2019.

The 36 states and FCT IGR figure hits N1.33trn in 2019 compared to N1.17trn recorded in 2018. This indicates a positive growth of 20.92% year on year.

Similarly, the Q4 2019 states and FCT IGR figure hits N346.20bn compared to N294.11bn recorded in Q3 2019. This indicates a positive growth of 17.71% quarter on quarter.

Lagos state has the highest Internally Generated Revenue with N398.73bn recorded, closely followed by Rivers with N140.40bn while Taraba State recorded the least Internally Generated revenue.

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ABIA STATE

Land Area: 2,440 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N52,039,868,624.86

Total Revenue Available 2019
N66,809,176,283.42

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.10

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.11

Total Revenue Available 2018
N70,161,217,967.64

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-4.78

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
78

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
22

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N4,059,982,019.86

Q2
N3,852,614,312.19

Q3
N2,695,809,294.50

Q4
N4,160,902,032.01

Total Tax 2019
N14,769,307,658.56

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-0.44

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth %
-13.81

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth %
54.35

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N4,160,902,032.01

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,078,584,551.71	N130,102,985.86	N134,951,550.00	N860,016,991.29	N2,203,656,078.86	N1,957,245,953.15

Share to Total
Growth %
1.11

TOTAL IGR
N14,769,307,658.56

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N5,905,155,132.15	N465,883,488.65	N425,906,571.16	N2,170,964,181.78	N8,967,909,373.74	N5,801,398,284.82

Abia - Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Abia - FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ADAMAWA STATE

Land Area: 14, 254 sq mi

FAAC 2019

N48,338,702,097.28

Total Revenue Available 2019

N58,043,362,282.70

% Share of
FAAC 2019

1.95

% Share of
IGR 2019

0.73

Total Revenue Available 2018

N55,715,083,240.01

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %

4.18

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

83.28

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

16.72

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR

N2,887,941,409.73

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,028,362,887.86	N29,332,052.76	N43,487,690.00	N156,858,314.39	N1,258,040,945.01	N1,629,900,464.72

Share to Total
Growth %

0.73

TOTAL IGR

N9,704,660,185.42

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N5,751,781,494.62	N118,856,369.70	N249,593,415.00	N556,974,166.14	N6,677,205,445.46	N3,027,454,739.96

Adamawa- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Adamawa- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

AKWA IBOM STATE

Land Area: 2,734 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N171,975,537,274.47

Total Revenue Available 2019
N204,266,552,045.992

% Share of
FAAC 2019
6.95

% Share of
IGR 2019
2.42

Total Revenue Available 2018
N226,575,882,622.71

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-9.85**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **84**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **16**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N6,574,351,082.08

Q2
N13,890,256,151.33

Q3
N6,150,553,510.00

Q4
N5,675,854,028.11

Total Tax 2019
N32,291,014,771.52

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **33.37**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **0.06**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-7.72**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N5,675,854,028.11**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N3,714,302,363.38	N33,359,719.90	N96,761,875.00	N943,528,111.77	N4,787,952,070.05	N887,901,958.06

Share to Total
Growth % **2.42**

TOTAL IGR **N32,291,014,771.52**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N24,640,620,075.97	N282,115,834.07	N380,133,180.00	N3,331,751,269.20	N28,634,620,359.24	N3,656,394,412.28

Akwa Ibom- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Akwa Ibom- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ANAMBRA STATE

Land Area: 1,870 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N53,893,862,221.01

Total Revenue Available 2019
N80,263,058,085.90

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.18

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.98

Total Revenue Available 2018
N74,555,213,544.25

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **7.66**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **67**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **33**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N4,528,819,102.03

Q2
N4,158,279,214.18

Q3
N8,171,092,757.15

Q4
N9,511,004,791.53

Total Tax 2019
N26,369,195,864.89

YoY (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **36.59**

YoY (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **16.88**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **16.40**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N9,511,004,791.53

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,708,499,891.95	N131,924,521.24	N256,748,975.00	N1,730,254,656.01	N3,827,428,044.20	N5,683,576,747.33

Share to Total
Growth % **1.98**

TOTAL IGR
N26,369,195,864.89

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N11,186,201,113.59	N679,424,931.30	N712,261,535.00	N3,554,911,041.19	N16,132,798,621.08	N10,236,397,243.81

Anambra- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Anambra- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

BAUCHI STATE

Land Area: 18,965 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N52,357,124,339.87

Total Revenue Available 2019
N64,054,080,224.62

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.12

% Share of
IGR 2019
0.88

Total Revenue Available 2018
N63,711,681,751.95

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **0.54**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **82**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **18**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N2,646,492,463.86

Q2
N5,622,215,674.33

Q3
N1,748,257,254.48

Q4
N1,679,990,492.08

Total Tax 2019
N11,696,955,884.75

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **20.70**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-36.55**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-3.90**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N1,679,990,492.08**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,504,575,816.54	N3,861,900.00	N39,396,450.00	N78,089,595.17	N1,625,923,761.71	N54,066,730.37

Share to Total
Growth % **0.88**

TOTAL IGR **N11,696,955,884.75**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N10,957,758,055.43	N29,864,538.49	N136,706,647.77	N390,617,015.29	N11,514,946,256.98	N182,009,627.77

Bauchi- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Bauchi- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

BAYELSA STATE

Land Area: 8,150 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N140,129,363,936.74

Total Revenue Available 2019
N156,472,126,468.72

Total Revenue Available 2018
N166,741,411,990.33

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N2,998,592,900.29

Q2
N2,876,925,918.38

Q3
N2,494,884,003.39

Q4
N7,972,359,709.92

Total Tax 2019
N16,342,762,531.98

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N7,972,359,709.92**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N7,633,726,149.31	N17,190,790.81	N5,747,371.37	N276,517,338.14	N7,933,181,649.63	N39,178,060.29

TOTAL IGR **N16,342,762,531.98**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N14,825,487,528.45	N283,581,024.00	N59,152,675.64	N927,723,389.79	N16,095,944,617.88	N246,817,914.10

Bayelsa- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Bayelsa- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

BENUE STATE

Land Area: 13,150 sq m

FAAC 2019
N54,340,296,718.03

Total Revenue Available 2019
N72,190,777,107.60

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.20

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.34

Total Revenue Available 2018
N66,656,560,913.88

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **8.30**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **75**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **25**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N2,827,145,731.90

Q2
N9,304,626,234.34

Q3
N2,799,585,180.17

Q4
N2,919,123,243.16

Total Tax 2019
N17,850,480,389.57

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **59.16**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **3.25**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **4.27**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N2,919,123,243.16**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,694,084,568.47	N142,549,620.59	N56,284,130.00	N52,327,991.57	N1,945,246,310.63	N973,876,932.53

Share to Total
Growth % **1.34**

TOTAL IGR **N17,850,480,389.57**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N13,306,462,021.08	N610,811,500.50	N457,188,304.00	N196,888,522.14	N14,571,350,347.72	N3,279,130,041.85

Benue- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Benue- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

BORNO STATE

Land Area: 22, 316 sq mi

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N2,134,157,412.85**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,011,664,628.62	N163,282,427.23	N95,128,486.00	N168,987,398.00	N1,439,062,939.85	N695,094,473.00

Share to Total Growth %
0.61

TOTAL IGR **N8,175,248,326.42**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N4,189,761,148.23	N540,030,198.11	N330,389,410.00	N804,282,502.06	N5,864,463,258.40	N2,310,785,068.02

Borno- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Borno- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

CROSS RIVER STATE

Land Area: 7,782 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N36,312,879,237.96

Total Revenue Available 2019
N58,909,943,120.51

% Share of
FAAC 2019
1.47

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.69

Total Revenue Available 2018
N54,506,799,760.22

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **8.08**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **62**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **38**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N3,227,417,722.92

Q2
N13,504,007,770.85

Q3
N2,884,355,555.33

Q4
N2,981,282,833.45

Total Tax 2019
N22,597,063,882.55

YoY (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **28.74**

YoY (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-34.85**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **3.36**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N2,981,282,833.45**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,665,457,692.41	N28,641,153.23	N195,886,755.11	N356,029,809.28	N2,246,015,410.03	N735,267,423.42

Share to Total
Growth % **1.69**

TOTAL IGR **N22,597,063,882.55**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N6,503,997,209.51	N106,572,646.32	N850,364,527.74	N11,746,317,956.34	N19,207,252,339.91	N3,389,811,542.64

Cross River- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Cross River- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

DELTA STATE

Land Area: 6,833 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N219,282,893,930.70

Total Revenue Available 2019
N283,961,690,922.27

% Share of
FAAC 2019
8.87

% Share of
IGR 2019
4.85

Total Revenue Available 2018
N272,073,791,302.60

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **4.37**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **77**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **23**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N17,487,284,334.79

Q2
N18,903,405,587.09

Q3
N13,119,344,029.20

Q4
N15,168,763,040.49

Total Tax 2019
N64,678,796,991.57

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **10.68**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-2.11**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **15.62**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N15,168,763,040.49

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N10,173,254,849.32	N69,875,216.89	N209,224,930.25	N1,903,620,818.83	N12,355,975,815.29	N2,812,787,225.20

Share to Total
Growth % **4.85**

TOTAL IGR
N64,678,796,991.57

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N47,702,984,808.00	N385,348,647.73	N790,122,854.90	N7,790,133,121.95	N56,668,589,432.58	N8,010,207,558.99

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

EBONYI STATE

Land Area: 2,136 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N44,627,158,742.33

Total Revenue Available 2019
N52,082,453,418.92

% Share of
FAAC 2019
1.80

% Share of
IGR 2019
0.56

Total Revenue Available 2018
N51,099,596,507.94

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **1.92**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **86**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **14**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,634,095,811.46

Q2
N2,281,715,517.33

Q3
N1,724,540,388.72

Q4
N1,814,942,959.08

Total Tax 2019
N7,455,294,676.59

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **21.33**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **2.07**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **5.24**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N1,814,942,959.08**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,087,882,109.89	N62,643,767.71	N48,632,260.00	N383,525,778.87	N1,582,683,916.47	N232,259,042.61

Share to Total
Growth % **0.56**

TOTAL IGR **N7,455,294,676.59**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N4,654,497,907.18	N93,324,825.43	N238,401,030.00	N1,330,066,456.36	N6,316,290,218.97	N1,139,004,457.62

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

EDO STATE

Land Area: 6,873 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N64,679,690,145.36

Total Revenue Available 2019
N94,158,096,169.67

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.62

% Share of
IGR 2019
2.21

Total Revenue Available 2018
N97,595,143,525.59

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-3.52**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **69**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **31**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N7,231,168,738.92

Q2
N8,210,580,135.58

Q3
N6,823,190,688.52

Q4
N7,213,466,461.29

Total Tax 2019
N29,478,406,024.31

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **3.70**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-4.48**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **5.72**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N7,213,466,461.29**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N3,620,823,855.82	N269,027,095.41	N169,123,360.66	N828,349,498.94	N4,887,323,810.83	N2,326,142,650.46

Share to Total
Growth % **2.21**

TOTAL IGR **N29,478,406,024.31**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N13,144,168,252.48	N1,048,070,372.43	N664,308,259.68	N7,324,600,911.11	N22,181,147,795.70	N7,297,258,228.61

Edo- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Edo- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

EKITI STATE

Land Area: 2,453 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N41,286,185,929.89

Total Revenue Available 2019
N49,833,061,578.13

Total Revenue Available 2018
N45,791,036,144.28

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,602,486,579.41

Q2
N1,730,141,204.15

Q3
N3,250,913,566.97

Q4
N1,963,334,297.71

Total Tax 2019
N8,546,875,648.24

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N1,963,334,297.71**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,289,603,186.58	N101,421,498.94	N31,774,715.00	N354,971,764.66	N1,777,771,165.18	N185,563,132.53

TOTAL IGR **N8,546,875,648.24**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N4,474,115,200.14	N303,892,108.94	N127,766,609.95	N2,712,938,440.99	N7,618,712,360.02	N928,163,288.22

Ekiti- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Ekiti- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ENUGU STATE

Land Area: 2,765 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N51,984,942,970.06

Total Revenue Available 2019
N83,054,409,883.06

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.10

% Share of
IGR 2019
2.33

Total Revenue Available 2018
N75,250,392,365.92

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **10.37**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **63**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **37**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N5,914,842,131.00

Q2
N4,784,207,653.00

Q3
N4,184,671,523.00

Q4
N16,185,745,606.00

Total Tax 2019
N31,069,466,913.00

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **40.29**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **183.85**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **286.79**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N16,185,745,606.00**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N11,681,026,520.00	N15,795,944.00	N269,488,775.00	N1,457,012,078.00	N13,423,323,317.00	N2,762,422,289.00

Share to Total
Growth % **2.33**

TOTAL IGR **N31,069,466,913.00**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N18,109,354,171.00	N153,691,242.00	N859,519,750.00	N2,661,603,257.00	N21,784,168,420.00	N9,285,298,493.00

Enugu- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Enugu- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

GOMBE STATE

Land Area: 7, 246 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N41,019,881,265.47

Total Revenue Available 2019
N 47,822,946,079.57

% Share of
FAAC 2019
1.66

% Share of
IGR 2019
0.51

Total Revenue Available 2018
N51,151,677,198.33

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-6.51**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **86**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **14**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total Tax 2019
N1,047,489,602.33	N 1,039,941,528.09	N 2,152,817,576.04	N2,562,816,107.64	N6,803,064,814.10

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-7.36**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-30.45**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **19.04**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N2,562,816,107.64**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N682,284,971.10	N2,024,030.06	N25,399,600.00	N127,868,397.24	N837,576,998.40	N1,725,239,109.24

Share to Total
Growth % **0.51**

TOTAL IGR **N6,803,064,814.10**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 2,870,000,110.21	N8,560,411.48	N106,653,925.00	N1,663,734,745.57	N4,648,949,192.26	N2,154,115,621.84

Gombe- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Gombe- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

IMO STATE

Land Area: 2,140 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N56,086,098,287.13

Total Revenue Available 2019
N72,181,397,907.72

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.27

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.21

Total Revenue Available 2018
N69,065,916,947.83

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **4.51**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **78**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **22**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N3,363,389,990.73

Q2
N7,186,998,160.57

Q3
N2,556,557,822.38

Q4
N 2,988,353,646.91

Total Tax 2019
N16,095,299,620.59

YoY (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **8.14**

YoY (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-12.03**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **16.89**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N2,988,353,646.91**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N2,218,545,849.35	N229,408,333.60	N151,091,600.80	N132,429,997.02	N2,731,475,780.77	N 256,877,866.14

Share to Total
Growth % **1.21**

TOTAL IGR **N16,095,299,620.59**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N12,421,874,604.41	N1,258,033,759.64	N901,847,432.36	N672,758,319.12	N15,254,514,115.53	N840,785,505.06

Imo- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Imo- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

JIGAWA STATE

Land Area: 8, 940 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N58,858,181,316.18

Total Revenue Available 2019
N71,784,839,462.47

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N69,574,177,146.68

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N3,050,962,933.41

Q2
N2,318,790,162.42

Q3
N3,688,887,463.32

Q4
N3,868,017,587.14

Total Tax 2019
N12,926,658,146.29

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N3,868,017,587.14

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 1,442,879,625.82	N360,224,210.82	N120,320,414.61	N1,211,496,352.52	N3,134,920,603.77	N733,096,983.37

TOTAL IGR
N12,926,658,146.29

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N4,744,937,169.74	N776,224,822.63	N341,279,362.07	N 4,653,357,825.77	N10,515,799,180.21	N2,410,858,966.08

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KADUNA STATE

Land Area: 17,781 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N67,100,907,303.95

Total Revenue Available 2019
N112,057,483,887.33

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N98,296,328,162.50

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **14.00**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **60**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **40**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N8,363,902,329.17

Q2
N16,930,950,458.29

Q3
N 6,284,148,242.41

Q4
N13,377,575,553.51

Total Tax 2019
N44,956,576,583.38

YoY (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **52.67**

YoY (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **79.62**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **112.88**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N13,377,575,553.51**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N3,139,178,349.34	N64,334,355.14	N155,652,037.00	N1,123,324,642.46	N4,482,489,383.94	N8,895,086,169.57

Share to Total
Growth % **3.37**

TOTAL IGR **N44,956,576,583.38**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N11,692,318,351.28	N 232,321,229.04	N509,535,162.00	N 13,510,968,162.82	N25,945,142,905.14	N19,011,433,678.24

Kaduna- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Kaduna- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KANO STATE

Land Area: 7,773 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N 82,485,067,955.07

Total Revenue Available 2019
N123,078,769,287.55

% Share of
FAAC 2019
3.34

% Share of
IGR 2019
3.04

Total Revenue Available 2018
N128,313,273,351.46

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-4.08

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
67

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
33

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N7,465,493,878.69

Q2
N11,099,052,225.67

Q3
N7,240,785,320.08

Q4
N14,788,369,908.04

Total Tax 2019
N40,593,701,332.48

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-7.97

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth %
-19.90

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth %
104.24

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N 14,788,369,908.04

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N3,551,833,327.75	N98,591,768.35	N220,478,003.30	N9,613,661,630.03	N13,484,564,729.43	N1,303,805,178.61

Share to Total
Growth %
3.04

TOTAL IGR
N40,593,701,332.48

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N14,805,541,623.51	N356,818,583.20	N545,446,262.76	N 16,273,348,599.96	N31,981,155,069.43	N 8,612,546,263.05

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KATSINA STATE

Land Area: 9,341 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N63,256,905,564.21

Total Revenue Available 2019
N71,753,647,683.21

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N68,613,353,789.57

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **4.58**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **88**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **12**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,769,760,638.00

Q2
N3,037,310,443.00

Q3
N 1,802,476,407.00

Q4
N1,887,194,631.00

Total Tax 2019
N 8,496,742,119.00

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **22.05**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **1.34**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **4.70**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N1,887,194,631.00**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,625,701,638.00	N61,791,754.00	N36,298,470.00	N88,084,754.00	N1,811,876,616.00	N75,318,015.00

Share to Total
Growth % **0.64**

TOTAL IGR **N8,496,742,119.00**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N7,441,156,095.00	N213,914,364.00	N123,899,889.00	N347,111,339.00	N8,126,081,687.00	N 370,660,432.00

Katsina- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Katsina- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KEBBI STATE

Land Area: 14,200 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N52,903,252,905.60

Total Revenue Available 2019
N60,270,587,742.73

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N59,462,137,460.36

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **1.36**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **88**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **12**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,461,294,729.82

Q2
N3,294,206,612.27

Q3
N1,204,820,823.22

Q4
N1,407,012,671.82

Total Tax 2019
N7,367,334,837.13

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **50.91**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-17.48**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **16.78**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N1,407,012,671.82**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N701,172,698.41	N330,192,658.41	N12,407,480.00	N44,757,817.00	N1,088,530,653.82	N318,482,018.00

Share to Total
Growth % **0.55**

TOTAL IGR **N7,367,334,837.13**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 5,151,544,695.55	N742,641,589.18	N59,138,323.00	N318,587,146.77	N6,271,911,754.50	N1,095,423,082.63

Kebbi- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Kebbi- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KOGI STATE

Land Area: 11,519 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N52,336,274,793.13

Total Revenue Available 2019
N68,725,301,181.99

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.12

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.23

Total Revenue Available 2018
N72,688,767,694.49

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-5.45**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **76**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **24**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N3,176,106,520.69

Q2
N3,507,701,544.01

Q3
N5,899,029,785.47

Q4
N3,806,188,538.69

Total Tax 2019
N16,389,026,388.86

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **44.60**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **13.40**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-35.48**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N3,806,188,538.69

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N2,434,149,982.97	N 8,945,033.79	N109,534,500.00	N 261,058,317.37	N2,813,687,834.13	N992,500,704.56

Share to Total
Growth % **1.23**

TOTAL IGR
N16,389,026,388.86

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N11,098,952,761.14	N62,204,945.57	N552,617,800.00	N1,339,883,902.52	N13,053,659,409.23	N3,335,366,979.63

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

KWARA STATE

Land Area: 14, 218 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N42,432,526,858.74

Total Revenue Available 2019
N73,079,258,267.66

% Share of
FAAC 2019

1.72

% Share of
IGR 2019

2.3

Total Revenue Available 2018
N67,620,175,560.78

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **8.07**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **58**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **42**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N6,276,779,069.16

Q2
N9,813,594,473.77

Q3
N7,910,423,599.11

Q4
N6,645,934,266.88

Total Tax 2019
N30,646,731,408.92

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **32.98**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-5.52**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-15.99**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N6,645,934,266.88**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,388,815,223.40	N299,410,493.00	N124,147,215.47	N 69,026,492.22	N1,881,399,424.09	N 4,764,534,842.79

Share to Total
Growth % **2.3**

TOTAL IGR **N30,646,731,408.92**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N11,364,149,817.33	N1,093,196,719.50	N494,512,711.04	N342,454,288.80	N13,294,313,536.67	N17,352,417,872.25

Kwara - Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Kwara - FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

LAGOS STATE

Land Area: 1,381 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N117,883,619,963.70

Total Revenue Available 2019
N516,615,866,457.08

% Share of
FAAC 2019
4.77

% Share of
IGR 2019
29.88

Total Revenue Available 2018
N501,205,576,422.67

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **3.07**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **23**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **77**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N97,475,046,701.01

Q2
N107,688,340,066.04

Q3
N91,933,017,729.18

Q4
N101,635,841,997.15

Total Tax 2019
N398,732,246,493.38

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **4.33**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **2.95**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **10.55**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N101,635,841,997.15**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N67,679,491,595.21	N 3,135,546,515.63	N2,591,399,530.95	N15,267,257,845.41	N88,673,695,487.20	N12,962,146,509.95

Share to Total
Growth % **29.88**

TOTAL IGR **N398,732,246,493.38**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N269,962,755,085.02	N16,023,351,961.60	N9,760,460,786.87	N63,577,475,171.62	N359,324,043,005.11	N39,408,203,488.27

Lagos - Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Lagos - FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

NASARAWA STATE

Land Area: 10,470 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N44,865,859,450.71

Total Revenue Available 2019
N55,724,681,873.69

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N55,117,135,184.88

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,714,704,933.63

Q2
N3,127,608,188.55

Q3
N3,006,864,232.06

Q4
N3,009,645,068.74

Total Tax 2019
N10,858,822,422.98

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N3,009,645,068.74

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,398,974,940.52	N 9,767,980.22	N50,753,458.25	N158,544,185.52	N1,618,040,564.51	N 1,391,604,504.23

TOTAL IGR
N10,858,822,422.98

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N7,048,363,079.71	N 46,537,742.52	N192,113,145.25	N 304,143,208.34	N7,591,157,175.82	N3,267,665,247.16

Nassarawa- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Nassarawa- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

NIGER STATE

Land Area: 29,484 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N56,447,911,750.79

Total Revenue Available 2019
N 69,212,946,723.09

% Share of
FAAC 2019

2.28

% Share of
IGR 2019

0.96

Total Revenue Available 2018
N67,953,800,532.59

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **1.85**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **82**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **18**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,768,201,722.47

Q2
N7,358,548,571.42

Q3
N2,140,043,248.37

Q4
N1,498,241,430.04

Total Tax 2019
N12,765,034,972.30

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **22.36**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-61.74**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-29.99**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR

N80,823,759.06

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,066,941,161.37	N 58,746,150.90	N73,549,732.00	N218,180,626.71	N1,417,417,670.98	N80,823,759.06

Share to Total
Growth % **0.96**

TOTAL IGR

N12,765,034,972.30

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 4,802,022,733.11	N166,113,602.82	N261,140,003.00	N7,072,556,375.19	N12,301,832,714.12	N 463,202,258.18

Niger- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Niger- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

OGUN STATE

Land Area: 6,556.23 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N38,710,634,518.43

Total Revenue Available 2019
N109,633,225,014.32

% Share of
FAAC 2019
1.57

% Share of
IGR 2019
5.32

Total Revenue Available 2018
N124,198,350,682.06

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-11.73**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **35**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **65**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N14,296,414,373.45

Q2
N15,287,065,065.39

Q3
N23,286,494,298.58

Q4
N18,052,616,758.47

Total Tax 2019
N70,922,590,495.89

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **-16.12**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **-15.87**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **-22.48**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N18,052,616,758.47

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N6,941,431,071.46	N 741,439,200.05	N214,350,713.27	N947,583,308.06	N 8,844,804,292.84	N9,207,812,465.63

Share to Total
Growth % **5.32**

TOTAL IGR
N70,922,590,495.89

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 24,301,801,617.66	N 2,755,655,556.12	N 976,746,375.85	N13,516,553,938.07	N41,550,757,487.70	N 29,371,833,008.19

Ogun- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Ogun- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ONDO STATE

Land Area: 6,000 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N57,927,048,890.29

Total Revenue Available 2019
N88,062,930,808.55

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.34

% Share of
IGR 2019
2.26

Total Revenue Available 2018
N89,474,787,548.44

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-1.58

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
66

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
34

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N5,198,098,998.27

Q2
N13,803,464,648.47

Q3
N5,534,717,016.79

Q4
N5,599,601,254.73

Total Tax 2019
N30,135,881,918.26

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth %
21.57

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth %
-45.77

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth %
1.17

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N5,599,601,254.73

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N2,034,952,963.17	N103,781,101.95	N248,767,225.46	N2,391,809,812.67	N4,779,311,103.25	N820,290,151.48

Share to Total
Growth %
2.26

TOTAL IGR
N30,135,881,918.26

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N17,178,310,537.41	N 548,108,654.34	N790,423,949.31	N8,142,724,357.18	N26,659,567,498.24	N3,476,314,420.02

Ondo- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Ondo- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

OSUN STATE

Land Area: 3,572 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N24,222,272,968.41

Total Revenue Available 2019
N42,144,667,491.84

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N33,218,969,112.52

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **26.87**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **57**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **43**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N4,755,285,019.49

Q2
N5,667,935,795.36

Q3
N3,730,731,770.44

Q4
N 3,768,441,938.14

Total Tax 2019
N17,922,394,523.43

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **72.64**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **31.32**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **1.01**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N3,768,441,938.14**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,487,512,553.76	N208,389,293.50	N42,718,858.00	N50,761,224.43	N1,789,381,929.69	N1,979,060,008.45

Share to Total
Growth % **1.34**

TOTAL IGR **N17,922,394,523.43**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N7,841,155,969.76	N897,206,841.86	N 205,690,159.24	N224,307,325.30	N9,168,360,296.16	N 8,754,034,227.27

Osun- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Osun- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

OYO STATE

Land Area: 10,986 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N55,800,604,161.25

Total Revenue Available 2019
N82,547,064,397.18

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.26

% Share of
IGR 2019
2.00

Total Revenue Available 2018
N83,924,234,062.99

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %
-1.64

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
68

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
32

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N6,623,203,309.61

Q2
N7,437,482,668.54

Q3
N5,943,668,543.02

Q4
N6,742,105,714.76

Total Tax 2019
N26,746,460,235.93

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth %
8.57

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth %
5.80

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth %
13.43

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N6,742,105,714.76

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N157,587,268.06	N4,053,366,392.43	N270,576,369.76	N863,162,083.47	N5,344,692,113.72	N1,397,413,601.04

Share to Total
Growth %
2.00

TOTAL IGR
N26,746,460,235.93

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N12,007,973,015.97	N4,539,854,753.30	N981,300,598.11	N3,490,555,728.05	N21,019,684,095.43	N5,726,776,140.50

Oyo- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Oyo- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

PLATEAU STATE

Land Area: 11, 936 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N42,224,236,190.96

Total Revenue Available 2019
N58,704,347,784.79

% Share of
FAAC 2019

1.71

% Share of
IGR 2019

1.24

Total Revenue Available 2018
N56,611,627,967.00

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **3.70**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **72**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **28**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N3,300,884,990.02

Q2
N6,113,067,281.49

Q3
N3,370,302,180.39

Q4
N3,695,857,141.93

Total Tax 2019
N16,480,111,593.83

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **29.49**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **15.64**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **9.66**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N 3,695,857,141.93**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N2,265,594,439.96	N 112,239,073.90	N 144,120,275.00	N613,931,792.53	N3,135,885,581.39	N559,971,560.54

Share to Total
Growth % **1.24**

TOTAL IGR **N16,480,111,593.83**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N9,629,425,996.38	N 153,169,104.94	N477,912,025.00	N 3,546,973,852.04	N13,807,480,978.36	N2,672,630,615.47

Plateau- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Plateau- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

RIVERS STATE

Land Area: 4,277 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N158,449,294,787.50

Total Revenue Available 2019
N 298,848,039,090.20

% Share of
FAAC 2019

6.41

% Share of
IGR 2019

10.52

Total Revenue Available 2018
N285,407,393,228.92

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **4.71**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **53**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **47**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N39,261,075,833.45

Q2
N 36,713,460,862.54

Q3
N31,051,532,678.27

Q4
N33,372,674,928.44

Total Tax 2019
N140,398,744,302.70

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **24.49**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **15.11**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **7.48**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N33,372,674,928.44

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N28,359,317,983.01	N429,716,261.61	N139,022,839.15	N3,139,155,037.14	N32,067,212,120.91	N1,305,462,807.53

Share to Total
Growth % **10.52**

TOTAL IGR
N140,398,744,302.70

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N101,088,167,770.00	N7,644,956,906.47	N 4,209,268,089.15	N21,266,417,312.42	N134,208,810,078.04	N6,189,934,224.66

Rivers- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Rivers- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

SOKOTO STATE

Land Area: 10,028 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N55,476,385,825.97

Total Revenue Available 2019
N74,481,479,367.08

% Share of
FAAC 2019
2.24

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.42

Total Revenue Available 2018
N73,222,065,855.52

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **1.72**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **74**

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019 **26**

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total Tax 2019
N1,721,848,237.57	N10,355,177,509.11	N2,278,854,786.80	N 4,649,213,007.63	N19,005,093,541.11
YoY (Annual) 2018 on 2019 Growth % 1.30	YoY (Quarterly) Q4 2018 on Q4 2019 Growth % -13.15	Q on Q Change (Q4 on Q3 2019) Growth % 104.02		

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N4,649,213,007.63**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 1,954,238,721.73	N5,898,821.25	N71,572,378.95	N 2,138,781,591.72	N4,170,491,513.65	N478,721,493.98

Share to Total
Growth % **1.42**

TOTAL IGR **N19,005,093,541.11**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 5,954,451,999.79	N43,276,921.25	N 120,386,173.95	N11,608,663,715.29	N17,726,778,810.28	N1,278,314,730.83

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

TARABA STATE

Land Area: 21, 032 sq mi

FAAC 2019

N46,515,352,151.03

Total Revenue Available 2019

N53,048,458,598.30

% Share of
FAAC 2019

1.88

% Share of
IGR 2019

0.49

Total Revenue Available 2018

N53,846,611,045.27

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %

-1.48

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

88

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

12

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Total Tax 2019
N1,400,198,737.81	N 1,872,018,802.05	N1,449,988,510.85	N 1,810,900,396.56	N 6,533,106,447.27

<p>↑</p> <p>Y on Y (Annual) 2018 on 2019 Growth %</p> <p>9.45</p>	<p>↓</p> <p>Y on Y (Quarterly) Q4 2018 on Q4 2019 Growth %</p> <p>-1.47</p>	<p>↑</p> <p>Q on Q Change (Q4 on Q3 2019) Growth %</p> <p>24.89</p>
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2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR

N 1,810,900,396.56

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 848,291,275.78	N54,521,710.81	N29,796,250.00	N5,212,852.26	N937,822,088.85	N873,078,307.71

↑

Share to Total
Growth %

0.49

TOTAL IGR

N 6,533,106,447.27

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N 3,232,292,703.54	N168,822,443.75	N103,225,400.00	N 67,554,279.50	N3,571,894,826.79	N 2,961,211,620.48

Taraba- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Taraba- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

YOBE STATE

Land Area: 17,568 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N 51,606,083,679.10

Total Revenue Available 2019
N60,050,717,778.19

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018
N57,257,208,718.97

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N1,220,712,367.51

Q2
N985,594,923.76

Q3
N1,136,975,201.59

Q4
N5,101,351,606.23

Total Tax 2019
N8,444,634,099.09

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR
N5,101,351,606.23

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N4,680,257,380.15	N 1,732,063.45	N122,840,735.00	N79,331,853.68	N4,784,162,032.28	N317,189,573.95

TOTAL IGR
N8,444,634,099.09

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N6,615,566,901.17	N6,346,451.31	N78,147,145.00	N401,931,822.19	N7,101,992,319.67	N1,342,641,779.42

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

ZAMFARA STATE

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N41,762,298,726.55

Total Revenue Available 2019
N57,178,342,126.31

% Share of
FAAC 2019
1.69

% Share of
IGR 2019
1.16

Total Revenue Available 2018
N49,038,520,686.74

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth % **16.60**

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
73

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019
27

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N2,366,586,564.59

Q2
N4,843,475,689.64

Q3
N3,382,897,683.87

Q4
N4,823,083,461.66

Total Tax 2019
N15,416,043,399.76

Y on Y (Annual)
2018 on 2019
Growth % **87.85**

Y on Y (Quarterly)
Q4 2018 on Q4 2019
Growth % **28.48**

Q on Q Change
(Q4 on Q3 2019)
Growth % **42.57**

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N4,823,083,461.66**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N1,223,447,738.48	N537,319,321.33	N754,900,000.00	N607,706,320.30	N3,123,373,380.11	N1,699,710,081.55

Share to Total
Growth % **1.16**

TOTAL IGR **N15,416,043,399.76**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N6,965,260,319.96	N1,672,361,609.49	N2,196,928,000.00	N1,914,805,885.50	N12,749,355,814.95	N2,666,687,584.81

Zamfara- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Zamfara- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

FCT

Land Area: 667 sq mi

FAAC 2019
N71,905,269,001.29

Total Revenue Available 2019
N146,469,449,836.60

Total Revenue Available 2018
N138,689,593,595.34

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

Q1
N21,273,457,743.02

Q2
N17,297,437,207.25

Q3
N17,151,971,893.88

Q4
N18,841,313,991.16

Total Tax 2019
N74,564,180,835.31

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR **N18,841,313,991.16**

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N16,712,117,450.39	N643,987,406.93	N0.00	N1,485,209,133.84	N18,841,313,991.16	N0.00

TOTAL IGR **N74,564,180,835.31**

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N65,747,514,380.56	N3,161,782,231.56	-----	N5,654,884,223.19	N74,564,180,835.31	-----

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

TOTAL STATE

FAAC 2019

N2,473,237,965,275.64

Total Revenue Available 2019

N3,807,463,975,557.00

% Share of
FAAC 2019

% Share of
IGR 2019

Total Revenue Available 2018

N3,744,181,497,450.80

YoY
2018 on 2019
Growth %

1.68

% FAAC Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

65

% IGR Contribution
to Total Revenue
Available 2019

35

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (Q1 - Q4)

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

TOTAL IGR

N346,201,219,924.68

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N202,886,567,281.05	N12,750,382,625.70	N7,262,335,010.36	N50,188,426,212.52	N273,087,711,129.63	N73,113,508,795.05

Share to Total
Growth %

100.00

TOTAL IGR

N1,334,226,010,281.36

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS

PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue
N809,317,881,456.04	N47,672,928,933.24	N30,270,487,488.80	N225,411,523,755.55	N1,112,672,821,633.63	N221,553,188,647.73

Total- FY 2019 IGR COLLECTION

Total- Q4 2019 IGR COLLECTION

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE AT STATE LEVEL - Q4 2019 & FULL YEAR 2019

STATES RANK BY IGR (FULL YEAR IGR SHARE TO TOTAL)

STATE	TOTAL - IGR	% SHARE	STATE	TOTAL - IGR	% SHARE
LAGOS	N398,732,246,493.38	29.88	KOGI	N16,389,026,388.86	1.23
RIVERS	N140,398,744,302.70	10.52	BAYELSA	N16,342,762,531.98	1.22
FCT	N74,564,180,835.31	5.59	IMO	N16,095,299,620.59	1.21
OGUN	N70,922,590,495.89	5.32	ZAMFARA	N15,416,043,399.76	1.16
DELTA	N64,678,796,991.57	4.85	ABIA	N14,769,307,658.56	1.11
KADUNA	N44,956,576,583.38	3.37	JIGAWA	N12,926,658,146.29	0.97
KANO	N40,593,701,332.48	3.04	NIGER	N12,765,034,972.30	0.96
AKWA IBOM	N32,291,014,771.52	2.42	BAUCHI	N11,696,955,884.75	0.88
ENUGU	N31,069,466,913.00	2.33	NASARAWA	N10,858,822,422.98	0.81
KWARA	N30,646,731,408.92	2.30	ADAMAWA	N9,704,660,185.42	0.73
ONDO	N30,135,881,918.26	2.26	EKITI	N8,546,875,648.24	0.64
EDO	N29,478,406,024.31	2.21	KATSINA	N8,496,742,119.00	0.64
OYO	N26,746,460,235.93	2.00	YOBE	N8,444,634,099.09	0.63
ANAMBRA	N26,369,195,864.89	1.98	BORNO	N8,175,248,326.42	0.61
CROSS RIVER	N22,597,063,882.55	1.69	EBONYI	N7,455,294,676.59	0.56
SOKOTO	N19,005,093,541.11	1.42	KEBBI	N7,367,334,837.13	0.55
OSUN	N17,922,394,523.43	1.34	GOMBE	N6,803,064,814.10	0.51
BENUE	N17,850,480,389.57	1.34	TARABA	N6,533,106,447.27	0.49
PLATEAU	N16,480,111,593.83	1.24			

Methodology

States IGR data is computed by the National Bureau of Statistics and the Joint Tax Board from official records and submissions by the 36 State Boards of Internal Revenue. These submissions are then validated and authenticated by the Joint Tax Board which is chaired by the Federal Inland Revenue Service and has the National Bureau of Statistics and the 36 State Boards of Internal Revenue as members.

MDAs Revenues

These relate to revenues generated administratively by State MDAs during the course of providing various services to residents in the State

Direct Assessment

Direct Assessment may relate to a form of personal income tax used to assess tax for self employed individuals. With the self assessed tax, a new tax payer can assess him/herself, and pay the calculated amount. Direct assessment may also relate to those imposed on businesses especially (informal) by the state authorities based on the size of their activities.

Pay As You Earn (PAYE)

This is a form of personal income tax that refers to tax deducted directly from the wages and salaries of employees operating in the formal sector. All employers in Nigeria are responsible for deducting Pay As You Earn (PAYE) taxes from their employees' earnings.

Road Taxes

Road taxes are daily levies paid by commercial transporters operating within the states

Other Taxes

These include various taxes such as levies on market traders, land registration and other land related fees, development levies on individuals, pool betting/lottery/gaming fees, stamp duties on individuals etc.

Schedule To The Taxes And Levies

Approved List for Collection) (ACT AMENDMENT) ORDER, 2015.

1. Taxes Collected by the **Federal Government**

- Company income tax.
- Withholding tax on companies, residents of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and non-resident individuals.
- Petroleum profits tax.
- Education Tax.
- Value Added Tax.
- Capital gains tax on residents of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, corporate and non-resident individuals.
- National Information Technology Development Levy
- Stamp duties on bodies corporate and residents of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
- Personal income tax in respect of
 - a) Members of the armed forces.
 - b) Members of the Nigeria Police Force.
 - c) Residents of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja; and
 - d) Staff of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and non-resident individuals

2. Taxes and levies collected by the **State Government.**

- Personal income tax in respect of:
 - (a) Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE);
 - (b) Direct taxation (Self-assessment)

- Withholding tax for Individuals
- Capital gains tax for individuals
- Stamp duties on instruments executed by individuals.
- Pools betting, lotteries, gaming and casino taxes.
- Road tax.
- Business premises registration
- Development levy for individuals
- Naming of street registration fees in State Capitals.
- Right of Occupancy fees on lands owned by the State Government.
- Market taxes and levies where State finance is involved.
- Hotel, Restaurant or Event Centre Consumption Tax, where applicable
- Entertainment Tax, where applicable
- Environmental(Ecological) Fee or Levy
- Mining, Milling and Quarry Fees, where applicable
- Animal Trade Tax, where applicable
- Produce Sales Tax, where applicable
- Slaughter or Abattoir Fees, where state finance is involved
- Infrastructure Maintenance Charge or Levy, where applicable
- Fire Service Charge
- Economic Development Levy, where applicable
- Social Services Contribution Levy, where applicable
- Signage and Mobile Advertisement, Jointly collected by States and Local Governments
- Property Tax
- Land use charge, where applicable.

3. Taxes and Levies to be collected by **Local Government**

- Shops and, kiosks rates
- Tenement rates
- On and off liquor license fees
- Slaughter slab fees.
- Marriage, birth and death registration fees.
- Naming of street registration fee, excluding any street in the State Capital
- Right of Occupancy fee on lands in rural areas, excluding those collectable by the Federal and State Governments.
- Market taxes and levies excluding any market where State Finance is involved.
- Motor Park levies.
- Domestic animal license fees.
- Bicycle, truck, canoe, wheelbarrow and cart fees, other than a mechanically propelled truck.
- Cattle tax payable by cattle farmers only.
- Merriment and road closure levy.
- Radio and television license fees (other than radio and television transmitter).
- Vehicle radio license fee (to be imposed by the local government of the State in which the car is registered.
- Wrong parking charges.
- Public convenience, sewage and refuse disposal fees.
- Customary burial ground permit fees.
- Religious places establishment permit fees.
- Signboard and advertisement permit fees
- Wharf Landing Charge, where applicable

INTERNALLY GENERATED REVENUE OF STATES (q1 - q4)								
						Yr on Yr Change (Annual)	Yr on Yr Change (Quarterly)	Quarter on Quarter Change
State	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Total Tax 2019	2018 on 2019 Growth %	Q4 2018 on Q4 2019 Growth %	(Q4 on Q3 2019) Growth %
Abia	4,059,982,019.86	3,852,614,312.19	2,695,809,294.50	4,160,902,032.01	14,769,307,658.56	-0.44	-13.81	54.35
Adamawa	1,612,649,398.43	3,402,158,452.24	1,801,910,925.02	2,887,941,409.73	9,704,660,185.42	56.40	74.70	60.27
Akwa Ibom	6,574,351,082.08	13,890,256,151.33	6,150,553,510.00	5,675,854,028.11	32,291,014,771.52	33.37	0.06	-7.72
Anambra	4,528,819,102.03	4,158,279,214.18	8,171,092,757.15	9,511,004,791.53	26,369,195,864.89	36.59	16.88	16.40
Bauchi	2,646,492,463.86	5,622,215,674.33	1,748,257,254.48	1,679,990,492.08	11,696,955,884.75	20.70	-36.55	-3.90
Bayelsa	2,998,592,900.29	2,876,925,918.38	2,494,884,003.39	7,972,359,709.92	16,342,762,531.98	19.85	123.72	219.55
Benue	2,827,145,731.90	9,304,626,234.34	2,799,585,180.17	2,919,123,243.16	17,850,480,389.57	59.16	3.25	4.27
Borno	1,901,227,718.09	2,016,620,356.48	2,123,242,839.00	2,134,157,412.85	8,175,248,326.42	25.30	12.71	0.51
Cross River	3,227,417,722.92	13,504,007,770.85	2,884,355,555.33	2,981,282,833.45	22,597,063,882.55	28.74	-34.85	3.36
Delta	17,487,284,334.79	18,903,405,587.09	13,119,344,029.20	15,168,763,040.49	64,678,796,991.57	10.68	-2.11	15.62
Ebonyi	1,634,095,811.46	2,281,715,517.33	1,724,540,388.72	1,814,942,959.08	7,455,294,676.59	21.33	2.07	5.24
Edo	7,231,168,738.92	8,210,580,135.58	6,823,190,688.52	7,213,466,461.29	29,478,406,024.31	3.70	-4.48	5.72
Ekiti	1,602,486,579.41	1,730,141,204.15	3,250,913,566.97	1,963,334,297.71	8,546,875,648.24	32.19	-21.27	-39.61
Enugu	5,914,842,131.00	4,784,207,653.00	4,184,671,523.00	16,185,745,606.00	31,069,466,913.00	40.29	183.85	286.79
Gombe	1,047,489,602.33	1,039,941,528.09	2,152,817,576.04	2,562,816,107.64	6,803,064,814.10	-7.36	-30.45	19.04
Imo	3,363,389,990.73	7,186,998,160.57	2,556,557,822.38	2,988,353,646.91	16,095,299,620.59	8.14	-12.03	16.89
Jigawa	3,050,962,933.41	2,318,790,162.42	3,688,887,463.32	3,868,017,587.14	12,926,658,146.29	39.80	84.47	4.86
Kaduna	8,363,902,329.17	16,930,950,458.29	6,284,148,242.41	13,377,575,553.51	44,956,576,583.38	52.67	79.62	112.88
Kano	7,465,493,878.69	11,099,052,225.67	7,240,785,320.08	14,788,369,908.04	40,593,701,332.48	-7.97	-19.90	104.24
Katsina	1,769,760,638.00	3,037,310,443.00	1,802,476,407.00	1,887,194,631.00	8,496,742,119.00	22.05	1.34	4.70
Kebbi	1,461,294,729.82	3,294,206,612.27	1,204,820,823.22	1,407,012,671.82	7,367,334,837.13	50.91	-17.48	16.78
Kogi	3,176,106,520.69	3,507,701,544.01	5,899,029,785.47	3,806,188,538.69	16,389,026,388.86	44.60	13.40	-35.48
Kwara	6,276,779,069.16	9,813,594,473.77	7,910,423,599.11	6,645,934,266.88	30,646,731,408.92	32.98	-5.52	-15.99
Lagos	97,475,046,701.01	107,688,340,066.04	91,933,017,729.18	101,635,841,997.15	398,732,246,493.38	4.33	2.95	10.55
Nasarawa	1,714,704,933.63	3,127,608,188.55	3,006,864,232.06	3,009,645,068.74	10,858,822,422.98	43.50	38.73	0.09
Niger	1,768,201,722.47	7,358,548,571.42	2,140,043,248.37	1,498,241,430.04	12,765,034,972.30	22.36	-61.74	-29.99
Ogun	14,296,414,373.45	15,287,065,065.39	23,286,494,298.58	18,052,616,758.47	70,922,590,495.89	-16.12	-15.87	-22.48
Ondo	5,198,098,998.27	13,803,464,648.47	5,534,717,016.79	5,599,601,254.73	30,135,881,918.26	21.57	-45.77	1.17
Osun	4,755,285,019.49	5,667,935,795.36	3,730,731,770.44	3,768,441,938.14	17,922,394,523.43	72.64	31.32	1.01
Oyo	6,623,203,309.61	7,437,482,668.54	5,943,668,543.02	6,742,105,714.76	26,746,460,235.93	8.57	5.80	13.43
Plateau	3,300,884,990.02	6,113,067,281.49	3,370,302,180.39	3,695,857,141.93	16,480,111,593.83	29.49	15.64	9.66
Rivers	39,261,075,833.45	36,713,460,862.54	31,051,532,678.27	33,372,674,928.44	140,398,744,302.70	24.49	15.11	7.48
Sokoto	1,721,848,237.57	10,355,177,509.11	2,278,854,786.80	4,649,213,007.63	19,005,093,541.11	1.30	-13.15	104.02
Taraba	1,400,198,737.81	1,872,018,802.05	1,449,988,510.85	1,810,900,396.56	6,533,106,447.27	9.45	-1.47	24.89
Yobe	1,220,712,367.51	985,594,923.76	1,136,975,201.59	5,101,351,606.23	8,444,634,099.09	92.70	240.73	348.68
Zamfara	2,366,586,564.59	4,843,475,689.64	3,382,897,683.87	4,823,083,461.66	15,416,043,399.76	87.85	28.48	42.57
FCT	21,273,457,743.02	17,297,437,207.25	17,151,971,893.88	18,841,313,991.16	74,564,180,835.31	13.80	15.89	9.85
Total	302,597,454,958.94	391,316,977,069.17	294,110,358,328.57	346,201,219,924.68	1,334,226,010,281.36	20.92	12.28	17.71

2019 FOURTH QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

S/N	State	PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue	Total IGR
1	Abia	1,078,584,551.71	130,102,985.86	134,951,550.00	860,016,991.29	2,203,656,078.86	1,957,245,953.15	4,160,902,032.01
2	Adamawa	1,028,362,887.86	29,332,052.76	43,487,690.00	156,858,314.39	1,258,040,945.01	1,629,900,464.72	2,887,941,409.73
3	Akwa Ibom	3,714,302,363.38	33,359,719.90	96,761,875.00	943,528,111.77	4,787,952,070.05	887,901,958.06	5,675,854,028.11
4	Anambra	1,708,499,891.95	131,924,521.24	256,748,975.00	1,730,254,656.01	3,827,428,044.20	5,683,576,747.33	9,511,004,791.53
5	Bauchi	1,504,575,816.54	3,861,900.00	39,396,450.00	78,089,595.17	1,625,923,761.71	54,066,730.37	1,679,990,492.08
6	Bayelsa	7,633,726,149.31	17,190,790.81	5,747,371.37	276,517,338.14	7,933,181,649.63	39,178,060.29	7,972,359,709.92
7	Benue	1,694,084,568.47	142,549,620.59	56,284,130.00	52,327,991.57	1,945,246,310.63	973,876,932.53	2,919,123,243.16
8	Borno	1,011,664,628.62	163,282,427.23	95,128,486.00	168,987,398.00	1,439,062,939.85	695,094,473.00	2,134,157,412.85
9	Cross River	1,665,457,692.41	28,641,153.23	195,886,755.11	356,029,809.28	2,246,015,410.03	735,267,423.42	2,981,282,833.45
10	Delta	10,173,254,849.32	69,875,216.89	209,224,930.25	1,903,620,818.83	12,355,975,815.29	2,812,787,225.20	15,168,763,040.49
11	Ebonyi	1,087,882,109.89	62,643,767.71	48,632,260.00	383,525,778.87	1,582,683,916.47	232,259,042.61	1,814,942,959.08
12	Edo	3,620,823,855.82	269,027,095.41	169,123,360.66	828,349,498.94	4,887,323,810.83	2,326,142,650.46	7,213,466,461.29
13	Ekiti	1,289,603,186.58	101,421,498.94	31,774,715.00	354,971,764.66	1,777,771,165.18	185,563,132.53	1,963,334,297.71
14	Enugu	11,681,026,520.00	15,795,944.00	269,488,775.00	1,457,012,078.00	13,423,323,317.00	2,762,422,289.00	16,185,745,606.00
15	Gombe	682,284,971.10	2,024,030.06	25,399,600.00	127,868,397.24	837,576,998.40	1,725,239,109.24	2,562,816,107.64
16	Imo	2,218,545,849.35	229,408,333.60	151,091,600.80	132,429,997.02	2,731,475,780.77	256,877,866.14	2,988,353,646.91
17	Jigawa	1,442,879,625.82	360,224,210.82	120,320,414.61	1,211,496,352.52	3,134,920,603.77	733,096,983.37	3,868,017,587.14
18	Kaduna	3,139,178,349.34	64,334,355.14	155,652,037.00	1,123,324,642.46	4,482,489,383.94	8,895,086,169.57	13,377,575,553.51
19	Kano	3,551,833,327.75	98,591,768.35	220,478,003.30	9,613,661,630.03	13,484,564,729.43	1,303,805,178.61	14,788,369,908.04
20	Katsina	1,625,701,638.00	61,791,754.00	36,298,470.00	88,084,754.00	1,811,876,616.00	75,318,015.00	1,887,194,631.00
21	Kebbi	701,172,698.41	330,192,658.41	12,407,480.00	44,757,817.00	1,088,530,653.82	318,482,018.00	1,407,012,671.82
22	Kogi	2,434,149,982.97	8,945,033.79	109,534,500.00	261,058,317.37	2,813,687,834.13	992,500,704.56	3,806,188,538.69
23	Kwara	1,388,815,223.40	299,410,493.00	124,147,215.47	69,026,492.22	1,881,399,424.09	4,764,534,842.79	6,645,934,266.88
24	Lagos	67,679,491,595.21	3,135,546,515.63	2,591,399,530.95	15,267,257,845.41	88,673,695,487.20	12,962,146,509.95	101,635,841,997.15
25	Nassarawa	1,398,974,940.52	9,767,980.22	50,753,458.25	158,544,185.52	1,618,040,564.51	1,391,604,504.23	3,009,645,068.74
26	Niger	1,066,941,161.37	58,746,150.90	73,549,732.00	218,180,626.71	1,417,417,670.98	80,823,759.06	1,498,241,430.04
27	Ogun	6,941,431,071.46	741,439,200.05	214,350,713.27	947,583,308.06	8,844,804,292.84	9,207,812,465.63	18,052,616,758.47
28	Ondo	2,034,952,963.17	103,781,101.95	248,767,225.46	2,391,809,812.67	4,779,311,103.25	820,290,151.48	5,599,601,254.73
29	Osun	1,487,512,553.76	208,389,293.50	42,718,858.00	50,761,224.43	1,789,381,929.69	1,979,060,008.45	3,768,441,938.14
30	Oyo	157,587,268.06	4,053,366,392.43	270,576,369.76	863,162,083.47	5,344,692,113.72	1,397,413,601.04	6,742,105,714.76
31	Plateau	2,265,594,439.96	112,239,073.90	144,120,275.00	613,931,792.53	3,135,885,581.39	559,971,560.54	3,695,857,141.93
32	Rivers	28,359,317,983.01	429,716,261.61	139,022,839.15	3,139,155,037.14	32,067,212,120.91	1,305,462,807.53	33,372,674,928.44
33	Sokoto	1,954,238,721.73	5,898,821.25	71,572,738.95	2,138,781,591.72	4,170,491,513.65	478,721,493.98	4,649,213,007.63
34	Taraba	848,291,275.78	54,521,710.81	29,796,250.00	5,212,852.26	937,822,088.85	873,078,307.71	1,810,900,396.56
35	Yobe	4,680,257,380.15	1,732,063.45	22,840,735.00	79,331,853.68	4,784,162,032.28	317,189,573.95	5,101,351,606.23
36	Zamfara	1,223,447,738.48	537,319,321.33	754,900,000.00	607,706,320.30	3,123,373,380.11	1,699,710,081.55	4,823,083,461.66
37	FCT	16,712,117,450.39	643,987,406.93	0.00	1,485,209,133.84	18,841,313,991.16	0.00	18,841,313,991.16
	Total	202,886,567,281.05	12,750,382,625.70	7,262,335,010.36	50,188,426,212.52	273,087,711,129.63	73,113,508,795.05	346,201,219,924.68

2019 FULL YEAR IGR COLLECTIONS ACROSS ALL STATES AND FCT IN NAIRA (NGN)

State	PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Tax	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue	Total	Share to Total
Abia	5,905,155,132.15	465,883,488.65	425,906,571.16	2,170,964,181.78	8,967,909,373.74	5,801,398,284.82	14,769,307,658.56	1.11
Adamawa	5,751,781,494.62	118,856,369.70	249,593,415.00	556,974,166.14	6,677,205,445.46	3,027,454,739.96	9,704,660,185.42	0.73
Akwa Ibom	24,640,620,075.97	282,115,834.07	380,133,180.00	3,331,751,269.20	28,634,620,359.24	3,656,394,412.28	32,291,014,771.52	2.42
Anambra	11,186,201,113.59	679,424,931.30	712,261,535.00	3,554,911,041.19	16,132,798,621.08	10,236,397,243.81	26,369,195,864.89	1.98
Bauchi	10,957,758,055.43	29,864,538.49	136,706,647.77	390,617,015.29	11,514,946,256.98	182,009,627.77	11,696,955,884.75	0.88
Bayelsa	14,825,487,528.45	283,581,024.00	59,152,675.64	927,723,389.79	16,095,944,617.88	246,817,914.10	16,342,762,531.98	1.22
Benue	13,306,462,021.08	610,811,500.50	457,188,304.00	196,888,522.14	14,571,350,347.72	3,279,130,041.85	17,850,480,389.57	1.34
Borno	4,189,761,148.23	540,030,198.11	330,389,410.00	804,282,502.06	5,864,463,258.40	2,310,785,068.02	8,175,248,326.42	0.61
Cross River	6,503,997,209.51	106,572,646.32	850,364,527.74	11,746,317,956.34	19,207,252,339.91	3,389,811,542.64	22,597,063,882.55	1.69
Delta	47,702,984,808.00	385,348,647.73	790,122,854.90	7,790,133,121.95	56,668,589,432.58	8,010,207,558.99	64,678,796,991.57	4.85
Ebonyi	4,654,497,907.18	93,324,825.43	238,401,030.00	1,330,066,456.36	6,316,290,218.97	1,139,004,457.62	7,455,294,676.59	0.56
Edo	13,144,168,252.48	1,048,070,372.43	664,308,259.68	7,324,600,911.11	22,181,147,795.70	7,297,258,228.61	29,478,406,024.31	2.21
Ekiti	4,474,115,200.14	303,892,108.94	127,766,609.95	2,712,938,440.99	7,618,712,360.02	928,163,288.22	8,546,875,648.24	0.64
Enugu	18,109,354,171.00	153,691,242.00	859,519,750.00	2,661,603,257.00	21,784,168,420.00	9,285,298,493.00	31,069,466,913.00	2.33
Gombe	2,870,000,110.21	8,560,411.48	106,653,925.00	1,663,734,745.57	4,648,949,192.26	2,154,115,621.84	6,803,064,814.10	0.51
Imo	12,421,874,604.41	1,258,033,759.64	901,847,432.36	672,758,319.12	15,254,514,115.53	840,785,505.06	16,095,299,620.59	1.21
Jigawa	4,744,937,169.74	776,224,822.63	341,279,362.07	4,653,357,825.77	10,515,799,180.21	2,410,858,966.08	12,926,658,146.29	0.97
Kaduna	11,692,318,351.28	232,321,229.04	509,535,162.00	13,510,968,162.82	25,945,142,905.14	19,011,433,678.24	44,956,576,583.38	3.37
Kano	14,805,541,623.51	356,818,583.20	545,446,262.76	16,273,348,599.96	31,981,155,069.43	8,612,546,263.05	40,593,701,332.48	3.04
Katsina	7,441,156,095.00	213,914,364.00	123,899,889.00	347,111,339.00	8,126,081,687.00	370,660,432.00	8,496,742,119.00	0.64
Kebbi	5,151,544,695.55	742,641,589.18	59,138,323.00	318,587,146.77	6,271,911,754.50	1,095,423,082.63	7,367,334,837.13	0.55
Kogi	11,098,952,761.14	62,204,945.57	552,617,800.00	1,339,883,902.52	13,053,659,409.23	3,335,366,979.63	16,389,026,388.86	1.23
Kwara	11,364,149,817.33	1,093,196,719.50	494,512,711.04	342,454,288.80	13,294,313,536.67	17,352,417,872.25	30,646,731,408.92	2.30
Lagos	269,962,755,085.02	16,023,351,961.60	9,760,460,786.87	63,577,475,171.62	359,324,043,005.11	39,408,203,488.27	398,732,246,493.38	29.88
Nasarawa	7,048,363,079.71	46,537,742.52	192,113,145.25	304,143,208.34	7,591,157,175.82	3,267,665,247.16	10,858,822,422.98	0.81
Niger	4,802,022,733.11	166,113,602.82	261,140,003.00	7,072,556,375.19	12,301,832,714.12	463,202,258.18	12,765,034,972.30	0.96
Ogun	24,301,801,617.66	2,755,655,556.12	976,746,375.85	13,516,553,938.07	41,550,757,487.70	29,371,833,008.19	70,922,590,495.89	5.32
Ondo	17,178,310,537.41	548,108,654.34	790,423,949.31	8,142,724,357.18	26,659,567,498.24	3,476,314,420.02	30,135,881,918.26	2.26
Osun	7,841,155,969.76	897,206,841.86	205,690,159.24	224,307,325.30	9,168,360,296.16	8,754,034,227.27	17,922,394,523.43	1.34
Oyo	12,007,973,015.97	4,539,854,753.30	981,300,598.11	3,490,555,728.05	21,019,684,095.43	5,726,776,140.50	26,746,460,235.93	2.00
Plateau	9,629,425,996.38	153,169,104.94	477,912,025.00	3,546,973,852.04	13,807,480,978.36	2,672,630,615.47	16,480,111,593.83	1.24
Rivers	101,088,167,770.00	7,644,956,906.47	4,209,268,089.15	21,266,417,312.42	134,208,810,078.04	6,189,934,224.66	140,398,744,302.70	10.52
Sokoto	5,954,451,999.79	43,276,921.25	120,386,173.95	11,608,663,715.29	17,726,778,810.28	1,278,314,730.83	19,005,093,541.11	1.42
Taraba	3,232,292,703.54	168,822,443.75	103,225,400.00	67,554,279.50	3,571,894,826.79	2,961,211,620.48	6,533,106,447.27	0.49
Yobe	6,615,566,901.17	6,346,451.31	78,147,145.00	401,931,822.19	7,101,992,319.67	1,342,641,779.42	8,444,634,099.09	0.63
Zamfara	6,965,260,319.96	1,672,361,609.49	2,196,928,000.00	1,914,805,885.50	12,749,355,814.95	2,666,687,584.81	15,416,043,399.76	1.16
FCT	65,747,514,380.56	3,161,782,231.56	-	5,654,884,223.19	74,564,180,835.31	-	74,564,180,835.31	5.59
TOTAL	809,317,881,456.04	47,672,928,933.24	30,270,487,488.80	225,411,523,755.55	1,112,672,821,633.63	221,553,188,647.73	1,334,226,010,281.36	100.00

2019 FULL YEAR IGR SHARE TO TOTAL

State	Total - IGR	Percentage Share (%)
Lagos	398,732,246,493.38	29.88
Rivers	140,398,744,302.70	10.52
FCT	74,564,180,835.31	5.59
Ogun	70,922,590,495.89	5.32
Delta	64,678,796,991.57	4.85
Kaduna	44,956,576,583.38	3.37
Kano	40,593,701,332.48	3.04
Akwa Ibom	32,291,014,771.52	2.42
Enugu	31,069,466,913.00	2.33
Kwara	30,646,731,408.92	2.30
Ondo	30,135,881,918.26	2.26
Edo	29,478,406,024.31	2.21
Oyo	26,746,460,235.93	2.00
Anambra	26,369,195,864.89	1.98
Cross River	22,597,063,882.55	1.69
Sokoto	19,005,093,541.11	1.42
Osun	17,922,394,523.43	1.34
Benue	17,850,480,389.57	1.34
Plateau	16,480,111,593.83	1.24
Kogi	16,389,026,388.86	1.23
Bayelsa	16,342,762,531.98	1.22
Imo	16,095,299,620.59	1.21
Zamfara	15,416,043,399.76	1.16
Abia	14,769,307,658.56	1.11
Jigawa	12,926,658,146.29	0.97
Niger	12,765,034,972.30	0.96
Bauchi	11,696,955,884.75	0.88
Nasarawa	10,858,822,422.98	0.81
Adamawa	9,704,660,185.42	0.73
Ekiti	8,546,875,648.24	0.64
Katsina	8,496,742,119.00	0.64
Yobe	8,444,634,099.09	0.63
Borno	8,175,248,326.42	0.61
Ebonyi	7,455,294,676.59	0.56
Kebbi	7,367,334,837.13	0.55
Gombe	6,803,064,814.10	0.51
Taraba	6,533,106,447.27	0.49

States	FAAC 2019 (N)	TOTAL REVENUE AVAILABLE TO STATES IN 2019				% Contribution to Total Revenue Available 2019		Total Revenue Available 2018 (N)	2019 ON 2018
		IGR 2019 (N)	Total Revenue Available 2019 (N)	% Share of Total FAAC 2019	% Share of Total State IGR 2019	FAAC	IGR		
Abia	52,039,868,624.86	14,769,307,658.56	66,809,176,283.42	2.10%	1.11%	77.89%	22.11%	70,161,217,967.64	-4.78%
Adamawa	48,338,702,097.28	9,704,660,185.42	58,043,362,282.70	1.95%	0.73%	83.28%	16.72%	55,715,083,240.01	4.18%
Akwa Ibom	171,975,537,274.47	32,291,014,771.52	204,266,552,045.99	6.95%	2.42%	84.19%	15.81%	226,575,882,622.71	-9.85%
Anambra	53,893,862,221.01	26,369,195,864.89	80,263,058,085.90	2.18%	1.98%	67.15%	32.85%	74,555,213,544.25	7.66%
Bauchi	52,357,124,339.87	11,696,955,884.75	64,054,080,224.62	2.12%	0.88%	81.74%	18.26%	63,711,681,751.95	0.54%
Bayelsa	140,129,363,936.74	16,342,762,531.98	156,472,126,468.72	5.67%	1.22%	89.56%	10.44%	166,741,411,990.33	-6.16%
Benue	54,340,296,718.03	17,850,480,389.57	72,190,777,107.60	2.20%	1.34%	75.27%	24.73%	66,656,560,913.88	8.30%
Borno	61,713,490,791.62	8,175,248,326.42	69,888,739,118.04	2.50%	0.61%	88.30%	11.70%	69,796,003,857.57	0.13%
Cross River	36,312,879,237.96	22,597,063,882.55	58,909,943,120.51	1.47%	1.69%	61.64%	38.36%	54,506,799,760.22	8.08%
Delta	219,282,893,930.70	64,678,796,991.57	283,961,690,922.27	8.87%	4.85%	77.22%	22.78%	272,073,791,302.60	4.37%
Ebonyi	44,627,158,742.33	7,455,294,676.59	52,082,453,418.92	1.80%	0.56%	85.69%	14.31%	51,099,596,507.94	1.92%
Edo	64,679,690,145.36	29,478,406,024.31	94,158,096,169.67	2.62%	2.21%	68.69%	31.31%	97,595,143,525.59	-3.52%
Ekiti	41,286,185,929.89	8,546,875,648.24	49,833,061,578.13	1.67%	0.64%	82.85%	17.15%	45,791,036,144.28	8.83%
Enugu	51,984,942,970.06	31,069,466,913.00	83,054,409,883.06	2.10%	2.33%	62.59%	37.41%	75,250,392,365.92	10.37%
Gombe	41,019,881,265.47	6,803,064,814.10	47,822,946,079.57	1.66%	0.51%	85.77%	14.23%	51,151,677,198.33	-6.51%
Imo	56,086,098,287.13	16,095,299,620.59	72,181,397,907.72	2.27%	1.21%	77.70%	22.30%	69,065,916,947.83	4.51%
Jigawa	58,858,181,316.18	12,926,658,146.29	71,784,839,462.47	2.38%	0.97%	81.99%	18.01%	69,574,177,146.68	3.18%
Kaduna	67,100,907,303.95	44,956,576,583.38	112,057,483,887.33	2.71%	3.37%	59.88%	40.12%	98,296,328,162.50	14.00%
Kano	82,485,067,955.07	40,593,701,332.48	123,078,769,287.55	3.34%	3.04%	67.02%	32.98%	128,313,273,351.46	-4.08%
Katsina	63,256,905,564.21	8,496,742,119.00	71,753,647,683.21	2.56%	0.64%	88.16%	11.84%	68,613,353,789.57	4.58%
Kebbi	52,903,252,905.60	7,367,334,837.13	60,270,587,742.73	2.14%	0.55%	87.78%	12.22%	59,462,137,460.36	1.36%
Kogi	52,336,274,793.13	16,389,026,388.86	68,725,301,181.99	2.12%	1.23%	76.15%	23.85%	72,688,767,694.49	-5.45%
Kwara	42,432,526,858.74	30,646,731,408.92	73,079,258,267.66	1.72%	2.30%	58.06%	41.94%	67,620,175,560.78	8.07%
Lagos	117,883,619,963.70	398,732,246,493.38	516,615,866,457.08	4.77%	29.88%	22.82%	77.18%	501,205,576,422.67	3.07%
Nasarawa	44,865,859,450.71	10,858,822,422.98	55,724,681,873.69	1.81%	0.81%	80.51%	19.49%	55,117,135,184.88	1.10%
Niger	56,447,911,750.79	12,765,034,972.30	69,212,946,723.09	2.28%	0.96%	81.56%	18.44%	67,953,800,532.59	1.85%
Ogun	38,710,634,518.43	70,922,590,495.89	109,633,225,014.32	1.57%	5.32%	35.31%	64.69%	124,198,350,682.06	-11.73%
Ondo	57,927,048,890.29	30,135,881,918.26	88,062,930,808.55	2.34%	2.26%	65.78%	34.22%	89,474,787,548.44	-1.58%
Osun	24,222,272,968.41	17,922,394,523.43	42,144,667,491.84	0.98%	1.34%	57.47%	42.53%	33,218,969,112.52	26.87%
Oyo	55,800,604,161.25	26,746,460,235.93	82,547,064,397.18	2.26%	2.00%	67.60%	32.40%	83,924,234,062.99	-1.64%
Plateau	42,224,236,190.96	16,480,111,593.83	58,704,347,784.79	1.71%	1.24%	71.93%	28.07%	56,611,627,967.00	3.70%
Rivers	158,449,294,787.50	140,398,744,302.70	298,848,039,090.20	6.41%	10.52%	53.02%	46.98%	285,407,393,228.92	4.71%
Sokoto	55,476,385,825.97	19,005,093,541.11	74,481,479,367.08	2.24%	1.42%	74.48%	25.52%	73,222,065,855.52	1.72%
Taraba	46,515,352,151.03	6,533,106,447.27	53,048,458,598.30	1.88%	0.49%	87.68%	12.32%	53,846,611,045.27	-1.48%
Yobe	51,606,083,679.10	8,444,634,099.09	60,050,717,778.19	2.09%	0.63%	85.94%	14.06%	57,257,208,718.97	4.88%
Zamfara	41,762,298,726.55	15,416,043,399.76	57,178,342,126.31	1.69%	1.16%	73.04%	26.96%	49,038,520,686.74	16.60%
FCT	71,905,269,001.29	74,564,180,835.31	146,469,449,836.60	2.91%	5.59%	49.09%	50.91%	138,689,593,595.34	5.61%
Total	2,473,237,965,275.64	1,334,226,010,281.36	3,807,463,975,557.00	100.00%	100.00%	64.96%	35.04%	3,744,181,497,450.80	1.69%

2019 FIRST QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

S/N	State	PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue	Total
1	Abia	1,442,590,359.20	48,319,298.68	52,234,000.00	329,859,739.31	1,873,003,397.19	2,186,978,622.67	4,059,982,019.86
2	Adamawa	1,146,963,393.31	17,056,345.00	146,029,025.00	63,217,607.34	1,373,266,370.65	239,383,027.78	1,612,649,398.43
3	Akwa Ibom	5,426,772,732.03	83,172,662.47	96,377,150.00	777,642,023.66	6,383,964,568.16	190,386,513.92	6,574,351,082.08
4	Anambra	2,072,249,130.00	176,222,769.10	142,716,212.00	437,728,944.18	2,828,917,055.28	1,699,902,046.75	4,528,819,102.03
5	Bauchi	2,431,810,527.24	14,058,506.06	19,725,044.74	146,423,418.64	2,612,017,496.68	34,474,967.18	2,646,492,463.86
6	Bayelsa	2,549,504,446.82	87,291,386.63	22,655,652.00	204,895,865.17	2,864,347,350.62	134,245,549.67	2,998,592,900.29
7	Benue	2,236,137,846.50	104,025,671.46	44,106,850.00	5,716,975.87	2,389,987,343.83	437,158,388.07	2,827,145,731.90
8	Borno	1,162,322,783.11	101,414,782.07	39,984,390.00	98,979,702.40	1,402,701,657.58	498,526,060.51	1,901,227,718.09
9	Cross River	1,737,997,008.38	28,384,972.19	247,530,074.16	191,886,624.87	2,205,798,679.60	1,021,619,043.32	3,227,417,722.92
10	Delta	13,150,741,612.69	129,416,695.79	206,738,635.48	1,577,186,821.00	15,064,083,764.96	2,423,200,569.83	17,487,284,334.79
11	Ebonyi	1,076,900,164.42	7,435,068.22	71,975,225.00	246,626,130.77	1,402,936,588.41	231,159,223.05	1,634,095,811.46
12	Edo	3,382,805,208.80	290,261,940.71	117,997,944.79	2,705,086,191.56	6,496,151,285.86	735,017,453.06	7,231,168,738.92
13	Ekiti	1,235,680,240.67	72,960,395.00	30,225,600.00	126,131,336.15	1,464,997,571.82	137,489,007.59	1,602,486,579.41
14	Enugu	2,432,369,009.00	39,700,544.00	145,445,119.00	364,511,621.00	2,982,026,293.00	2,932,815,838.00	5,914,842,131.00
15	Gombe	734,550,453.64	3,745,554.00	31,835,450.00	120,431,568.93	890,563,026.57	156,926,575.76	1,047,489,602.33
16	Imo	2,260,497,533.65	402,892,457.08	350,000,000.00	150,000,000.00	3,163,389,990.73	200,000,000.00	3,363,389,990.73
17	Jigawa	1,169,604,938.67	108,524,400.00	76,769,666.56	1,092,698,111.04	2,447,597,116.27	603,365,817.14	3,050,962,933.41
18	Kaduna	2,766,891,624.62	76,381,818.55	112,168,265.00	496,785,057.23	3,452,226,765.40	4,911,675,563.77	8,363,902,329.17
19	Kano	4,086,703,719.00	118,695,587.06	157,839,858.74	1,918,071,516.38	6,281,310,681.18	1,184,183,197.51	7,465,493,878.69
20	Katsina	1,514,836,632.00	26,517,229.00	28,203,315.00	100,851,377.00	1,670,408,553.00	99,352,085.00	1,769,760,638.00
21	Kebbi	812,527,278.53	116,975,997.26	4,140,700.00	112,662,376.02	1,046,306,351.81	414,988,378.01	1,461,294,729.82
22	Kogi	1,757,479,636.47	11,815,475.89	145,221,600.00	266,798,828.23	2,181,315,540.59	994,790,980.10	3,176,106,520.69
23	Kwara	1,608,876,285.79	215,816,407.49	124,289,367.00	161,408,851.58	2,110,390,911.86	4,166,388,157.30	6,276,779,069.16
24	Lagos	68,399,812,746.63	4,471,557,754.99	1,800,872,811.37	15,586,224,731.48	90,258,468,044.47	7,216,578,656.54	97,475,046,701.01
25	Nassarawa	1,228,728,033.36	12,052,078.00	46,110,791.70	61,826,498.41	1,348,717,401.47	365,987,532.16	1,714,704,933.63
26	Niger	1,245,246,170.33	25,005,557.23	57,160,940.00	274,427,752.91	1,601,840,420.47	166,361,302.00	1,768,201,722.47
27	Ogun	5,819,385,861.32	602,639,701.95	259,033,531.03	1,098,700,420.85	7,779,759,515.15	6,516,654,858.30	14,296,414,373.45
28	Ondo	1,891,950,745.89	193,719,636.49	91,275,816.92	2,280,308,410.92	4,457,254,610.22	740,844,388.05	5,198,098,998.27
29	Osun	1,527,990,069.70	215,679,695.43	63,425,575.00	61,941,506.51	1,869,036,846.64	2,886,248,172.85	4,755,285,019.49
30	Oyo	3,821,362,679.94	190,722,881.71	228,100,306.67	959,523,614.99	5,199,709,483.31	1,423,493,826.30	6,623,203,309.61
31	Plateau	1,872,911,294.20	10,813,964.40	107,605,425.00	632,777,936.99	2,624,108,620.59	676,776,369.43	3,300,884,990.02
32	Rivers	27,511,285,307.57	4,140,454,726.30	1,285,681,625.00	5,018,487,275.03	37,955,908,933.90	1,305,166,899.55	39,261,075,833.45
33	Sokoto	1,312,877,534.01	12,168,900.00	12,412,815.00	243,669,566.10	1,581,128,815.11	140,719,422.46	1,721,848,237.57
34	Taraba	530,816,494.32	26,426,180.14	23,078,175.00	41,390,644.82	621,711,494.28	778,487,243.53	1,400,198,737.81
35	Yobe	668,449,158.79	1,697,110.81	21,579,135.00	79,070,842.06	770,796,246.66	449,916,120.85	1,220,712,367.51
36	Zamfara	1,078,419,905.53	261,176,734.75	369,862,000.00	342,362,660.00	2,051,821,300.28	314,765,264.31	2,366,586,564.59
37	FCT	19,395,653,666.55	930,542,486.29	0.00	947,261,590.18	21,273,457,743.02	0.00	21,273,457,743.02
Total		194,501,702,232.68	13,375,743,372.20	6,780,408,092.16	39,323,574,139.58	253,981,427,836.62	48,616,027,122.32	302,597,454,958.94

2019 SECOND QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

S/N	State	PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue	Total
1	Abia	2,345,001,427.91	128,984,532.68	78,379,394.51	400,199,818.48	2,952,565,173.58	900,049,138.61	3,852,614,312.19
2	Adamawa	2,599,894,982.63	13,745,550.00	29,172,850.00	118,996,082.07	2,761,809,464.70	640,348,987.54	3,402,158,452.24
3	Akwa Ibom	12,081,190,434.56	68,043,949.70	93,134,750.00	724,390,919.77	12,966,760,054.03	923,496,097.30	13,890,256,151.33
4	Anambra	1,345,558,055.61	197,852,515.13	136,638,333.00	788,594,963.35	2,468,643,867.09	1,689,635,347.09	4,158,279,214.18
5	Bauchi	5,420,619,482.59	6,729,081.11	42,187,203.00	101,533,244.12	5,571,069,010.82	51,146,663.51	5,622,215,674.33
6	Bayelsa	2,398,909,028.26	108,280,821.97	18,376,471.46	314,950,814.19	2,840,517,135.88	36,408,782.50	2,876,925,918.38
7	Benue	8,016,895,387.61	201,898,862.49	139,864,878.00	36,110,184.00	8,394,769,312.10	909,856,922.24	9,304,626,234.34
8	Borno	1,115,289,337.51	119,225,961.40	96,998,417.00	158,198,971.31	1,489,712,687.22	526,907,669.26	2,016,620,356.48
9	Cross River	1,787,068,935.19	29,284,544.27	227,951,510.02	10,454,156,408.09	12,498,461,397.57	1,005,546,373.28	13,504,007,770.85
10	Delta	14,926,492,257.83	110,492,179.14	196,704,931.51	2,155,302,242.66	17,388,991,611.14	1,514,413,975.95	18,903,405,587.09
11	Ebonyi	1,419,036,976.55	7,521,724.00	57,299,775.00	286,583,590.98	1,770,442,066.53	511,273,450.80	2,281,715,517.33
12	Edo	3,008,631,502.55	286,858,863.68	174,162,023.75	2,810,743,524.93	6,280,395,914.91	1,930,184,220.67	8,210,580,135.58
13	Ekiti	1,132,648,175.82	60,971,292.00	31,778,520.00	138,005,577.43	1,363,403,565.25	366,737,638.90	1,730,141,204.15
14	Enugu	1,913,705,074.00	72,587,371.00	216,203,246.00	423,054,372.00	2,625,550,063.00	2,158,657,590.00	4,784,207,653.00
15	Gombe	657,582,142.51	1,771,988.00	26,636,000.00	142,110,944.01	828,101,074.52	211,840,453.57	1,039,941,528.09
16	Imo	6,329,407,822.61	322,896,482.96	320,000,000.00	120,000,000.00	7,092,304,305.57	94,693,855.00	7,186,998,160.57
17	Jigawa	725,472,821.14	7,035,834.00	11,304,300.00	1,041,206,125.51	1,785,019,080.65	533,771,081.77	2,318,790,162.42
18	Kaduna	2,855,794,830.69	65,473,735.98	112,769,965.00	11,369,203,230.96	14,403,241,762.63	2,527,708,695.66	16,930,950,458.29
19	Kano	3,742,555,998.15	79,674,180.52	28,309,976.43	4,204,812,822.31	8,055,352,977.41	3,043,699,248.26	11,099,052,225.67
20	Katsina	2,744,194,120.00	79,875,566.00	31,905,482.00	82,800,688.00	2,938,775,856.00	98,534,587.00	3,037,310,443.00
21	Kebbi	2,844,023,145.47	184,176,138.13	38,090,143.00	90,913,572.23	3,157,202,998.83	137,003,613.44	3,294,206,612.27
22	Kogi	2,192,375,097.19	18,623,510.02	195,180,400.00	238,596,238.21	2,644,775,245.42	862,926,298.59	3,507,701,544.01
23	Kwara	6,827,582,431.06	308,893,517.01	122,091,164.28	54,953,609.86	7,313,520,722.21	2,500,073,751.56	9,813,594,473.77
24	Lagos	73,531,618,835.54	5,231,716,014.30	2,352,078,242.47	16,429,063,307.24	97,544,476,399.55	10,143,863,666.49	107,688,340,066.04
25	Nassarawa	3,002,924,904.86	11,768,258.65	42,809,368.00	19,964,710.05	3,077,467,241.56	50,140,946.99	3,127,608,188.55
26	Niger	1,363,475,216.37	34,384,134.64	54,487,990.00	5,810,059,582.88	7,262,406,923.89	96,141,647.53	7,358,548,571.42
27	Ogun	5,357,694,349.31	661,529,432.11	266,254,993.75	1,010,569,403.69	7,296,048,178.86	7,991,016,886.53	15,287,065,065.39
28	Ondo	10,820,881,340.70	144,334,804.42	217,945,081.00	1,876,895,937.19	13,060,057,163.31	743,407,485.16	13,803,464,648.47
29	Osun	3,536,055,652.40	280,636,324.21	60,823,897.00	26,636,566.56	3,904,152,440.17	1,763,783,355.19	5,667,935,795.36
30	Oyo	4,163,399,980.34	151,418,132.01	238,910,195.83	1,056,934,661.33	5,610,662,969.51	1,826,819,699.03	7,437,482,668.54
31	Plateau	3,738,053,511.47	16,715,452.77	108,851,275.00	1,547,142,349.68	5,410,762,588.92	702,304,692.57	6,113,067,281.49
32	Rivers	22,682,729,159.77	2,332,797,874.21	1,684,196,550.00	7,748,545,124.19	34,448,268,708.17	2,265,192,154.37	36,713,460,862.54
33	Sokoto	1,297,667,149.54	13,671,600.00	11,689,423.00	8,886,425,960.15	10,209,454,132.69	145,723,376.42	10,355,177,509.11
34	Taraba	1,244,217,875.24	37,071,930.74	21,620,975.00	7,738,490.22	1,310,649,271.20	561,369,530.85	1,872,018,802.05
35	Yobe	528,254,119.20	1,631,406.00	16,299,900.00	97,215,246.30	643,400,671.50	342,194,252.26	985,594,923.76
36	Zamfara	3,457,600,168.97	338,715,019.24	354,966,000.00	451,888,209.50	4,603,169,397.71	240,306,291.93	4,843,475,689.64
37	FCT	14,646,868,911.52	857,491,223.75	0.00	1,793,077,071.98	17,297,437,207.25	0.00	17,297,437,207.25
Total		237,801,370,642.67	12,594,779,808.24	7,856,073,625.01	83,017,574,565.43	341,269,798,641.35	50,047,178,427.82	391,316,977,069.17

2019 THIRD QUARTER IGR COLLECTION

S/N	State	PAYE	Direct Assessment	Road Taxes	Other Taxes	Total Tax	MDAs Revenue	Total
1	Abia	1,038,978,793.33	158,476,671.43	160,341,626.65	580,887,632.70	1,938,684,724.11	757,124,570.39	2,695,809,294.50
2	Adamawa	976,560,230.82	58,722,421.94	30,903,850.00	217,902,162.34	1,284,088,665.10	517,822,259.92	1,801,910,925.02
3	Akwa Ibom	3,418,354,546.00	97,539,502.00	93,859,405.00	886,190,214.00	4,495,943,667.00	1,654,609,843.00	6,150,553,510.00
4	Anambra	6,059,894,036.03	173,425,125.83	176,158,015.00	598,332,477.65	7,007,809,654.51	1,163,283,102.64	8,171,092,757.15
5	Bauchi	1,600,752,229.06	5,215,051.32	35,397,950.03	64,570,757.36	1,705,935,987.77	42,321,266.71	1,748,257,254.48
6	Bayelsa	2,243,347,904.06	70,818,024.59	12,373,180.81	131,359,372.29	2,457,898,481.75	36,985,521.64	2,494,884,003.39
7	Benue	1,359,344,218.50	162,337,345.96	216,932,446.00	102,733,370.70	1,841,347,381.16	958,237,799.01	2,799,585,180.17
8	Borno	900,484,398.99	156,107,027.41	98,278,117.00	378,116,430.35	1,532,985,973.75	590,256,865.25	2,123,242,839.00
9	Cross River	1,313,473,573.53	20,261,976.63	178,996,188.45	744,245,114.10	2,256,976,852.71	627,378,702.62	2,884,355,555.33
10	Delta	9,452,496,088.16	75,564,555.91	177,454,357.66	2,154,023,239.46	11,859,538,241.19	1,259,805,788.01	13,119,344,029.20
11	Ebonyi	1,070,678,656.32	15,724,265.50	60,493,770.00	413,330,955.74	1,560,227,647.56	164,312,741.16	1,724,540,388.72
12	Edo	3,131,907,685.31	201,922,472.63	203,024,930.48	980,421,695.68	4,517,276,784.10	2,305,913,904.42	6,823,190,688.52
13	Ekiti	816,183,597.07	68,538,923.00	33,987,774.95	2,093,829,762.75	3,012,540,057.77	238,373,509.20	3,250,913,566.97
14	Enugu	2,082,253,568.00	25,607,383.00	228,382,610.00	417,025,186.00	2,753,268,747.00	1,431,402,776.00	4,184,671,523.00
15	Gombe	795,582,542.96	1,018,839.42	22,782,875.00	1,273,323,835.39	2,092,708,092.77	60,109,483.27	2,152,817,576.04
16	Imo	1,613,423,398.80	302,836,486.00	80,755,831.56	270,328,322.10	2,267,344,038.46	289,213,783.92	2,556,557,822.38
17	Jigawa	1,406,979,784.11	300,440,377.81	132,884,980.90	1,307,957,236.70	3,148,262,379.52	540,625,083.80	3,688,887,463.32
18	Kaduna	2,930,453,546.63	26,131,319.37	128,944,895.00	521,655,232.17	3,607,184,993.17	2,676,963,249.24	6,284,148,242.41
19	Kano	3,424,448,578.61	59,857,047.27	138,818,424.29	536,802,631.24	4,159,926,681.41	3,080,858,638.67	7,240,785,320.08
20	Katsina	1,556,423,705.00	45,729,815.00	27,492,622.00	75,374,520.00	1,705,020,662.00	97,455,745.00	1,802,476,407.00
21	Kebbi	793,821,573.14	111,296,795.38	4,500,000.00	70,253,381.52	979,871,750.04	224,949,073.18	1,204,820,823.22
22	Kogi	4,714,948,044.51	22,820,925.87	102,681,300.00	573,430,518.71	5,413,880,789.09	485,148,996.38	5,899,029,785.47
23	Kwara	1,538,875,877.08	269,076,302.00	123,984,964.29	57,065,335.14	1,989,002,478.51	5,921,421,120.60	7,910,423,599.11
24	Lagos	60,351,831,907.64	3,184,531,676.68	3,016,110,202.08	16,294,929,287.49	82,847,403,073.89	9,085,614,655.29	91,933,017,729.18
25	Nassarawa	1,417,735,200.97	12,949,425.65	52,439,527.30	63,807,814.36	1,546,931,968.28	1,459,932,263.78	3,006,864,232.06
26	Niger	1,126,360,185.04	47,977,760.05	75,941,341.00	769,888,412.69	2,020,167,698.78	119,875,549.59	2,140,043,248.37
27	Ogun	6,183,290,335.57	750,047,222.01	237,107,137.80	10,459,700,805.47	17,630,145,500.85	5,656,348,797.73	23,286,494,298.58
28	Ondo	2,430,525,487.65	106,273,111.48	232,435,825.93	1,593,710,196.40	4,362,944,621.46	1,171,772,395.33	5,534,717,016.79
29	Osun	1,289,597,693.90	192,501,528.72	38,721,829.24	84,968,027.80	1,605,789,079.66	2,124,942,690.78	3,730,731,770.44
30	Oyo	3,865,623,087.63	144,347,347.15	243,713,725.85	610,935,368.26	4,864,619,528.89	1,079,049,014.13	5,943,668,543.02
31	Plateau	1,752,866,750.75	13,400,613.87	117,335,050.00	753,121,772.84	2,636,724,187.46	733,577,992.93	3,370,302,180.39
32	Rivers	22,534,835,319.65	741,988,044.35	1,100,367,075.00	5,360,229,876.06	29,737,420,315.06	1,314,112,363.21	31,051,532,678.27
33	Sokoto	1,389,668,594.51	11,537,600.00	24,711,557.00	339,786,597.32	1,765,704,348.83	513,150,437.97	2,278,854,786.80
34	Taraba	608,967,058.20	50,802,622.06	28,730,000.00	13,212,292.20	701,711,972.46	748,276,538.39	1,449,988,510.85
35	Yobe	738,606,243.03	1,285,871.05	17,427,375.00	146,313,880.15	903,633,369.23	233,341,832.36	1,136,975,201.59
36	Zamfara	1,205,792,506.98	535,150,534.17	717,200,000.00	512,848,695.70	2,970,991,736.85	411,905,947.02	3,382,897,683.87
37	FCT	14,992,874,352.10	729,761,114.59	0.00	1,429,336,427.19	17,151,971,893.88	0.00	17,151,971,893.88
	Total	174,128,241,299.64	8,952,023,127.10	8,371,670,761.27	52,881,948,838.02	244,333,884,026.03	49,776,474,302.54	294,110,358,328.57

2018 Q1-Q4 IGR COLLECTION**†						
States/FCT	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	2018 Full Year	
Abia	3,381,405,773.46	3,595,598,485.61	3,030,430,890.30	4,827,469,298.12	14,834,904,447.49	Abia
Adamawa	1,399,656,160.16	1,776,834,470.06	1,375,273,320.45	1,653,112,714.95	6,204,876,665.62	Adamawa
Akwa Ibom	6,855,267,611.13	4,977,247,121.06	6,705,753,013.33	5,672,542,357.20	24,210,810,102.72	Akwa Ibom
Anambra	3,645,115,621.49	3,422,277,924.47	4,100,593,261.98	8,137,280,839.00	19,305,267,646.94	Anambra
Bauchi	2,050,106,131.84	2,556,334,669.28	2,436,811,723.03	2,647,579,653.43	9,690,832,177.58	Bauchi
Bayelsa	4,083,007,547.77	2,791,232,271.86	3,198,838,206.76	3,563,467,690.39	13,636,545,716.78	Bayelsa
Benue	2,737,672,598.74	3,326,033,449.05	2,324,630,945.47	2,827,145,731.90	11,215,482,725.16	Benue
Borno	1,499,060,122.50	1,561,598,789.73	1,570,198,517.00	1,893,443,474.83	6,524,300,904.06	Borno
Cross River	3,763,830,682.53	5,993,972,546.50	3,218,254,451.35	4,576,055,256.71	17,552,112,937.09	Cross River
Delta	16,343,107,878.09	13,454,284,995.72	13,147,112,578.30	15,495,093,220.20	58,439,598,672.31	Delta
Ebonyi	1,541,367,369.29	1,504,987,769.20	1,320,081,796.37	1,778,150,130.79	6,144,587,065.65	Ebonyi
Edo	7,362,135,105.33	6,446,548,343.95	7,065,291,160.20	7,551,522,232.75	28,425,496,842.23	Edo
Ekiti	1,501,600,288.90	1,243,343,208.97	1,226,709,405.75	2,493,721,347.03	6,465,374,250.65	Ekiti
Enugu	8,728,877,176.00	3,569,520,979.00	4,145,288,837.00	5,702,250,224.00	22,145,937,216.00	Enugu
Gombe	1,103,922,873.08	1,290,819,099.33	1,263,807,376.28	3,685,000,272.84	7,343,549,621.53	Gombe
Imo	3,592,852,650.20	3,419,328,542.07	4,475,133,205.45	3,396,957,412.59	14,884,271,810.31	Imo
Jigawa	2,146,456,700.57	2,655,293,886.58	2,347,712,138.63	2,096,788,110.25	9,246,250,836.03	Jigawa
Kaduna	8,839,906,826.29	7,164,587,629.09	5,994,244,850.56	7,447,647,618.80	29,446,386,924.74	Kaduna
Kano	9,292,824,304.63	9,261,711,800.26	7,090,379,424.19	18,462,459,755.17	44,107,375,284.25	Kano
Katsina	1,789,685,111.00	1,697,153,343.00	1,612,747,634.00	1,862,284,241.00	6,961,870,329.00	Katsina
Kebbi	1,017,839,463.35	1,016,412,663.69	1,142,753,947.59	1,704,954,931.15	4,881,961,005.78	Kebbi
Kogi	2,528,461,175.41	2,919,134,200.71	2,530,079,917.46	3,356,438,449.97	11,334,113,743.55	Kogi
Kwara	6,389,122,276.67	3,654,056,177.04	5,969,556,705.15	7,034,209,136.73	23,046,944,295.60	Kwara
Lagos	96,236,288,416.78	100,158,876,856.91	87,063,625,667.81	98,722,757,685.63	382,181,548,627.13	Lagos
Nassarawa	2,439,646,825.99	1,366,814,370.59	1,591,041,429.22	2,169,418,031.11	7,566,920,656.91	Nasarawa
Niger	2,288,238,354.26	2,572,387,120.05	1,656,022,919.64	3,915,542,562.68	10,432,190,956.63	Niger
Ogun	21,340,297,222.14	21,178,967,207.23	20,577,479,637.32	21,457,455,526.98	84,554,199,593.67	Ogun
Ondo	3,609,802,072.11	5,807,617,736.66	5,044,484,827.83	10,326,155,088.93	24,788,059,725.53	Ondo
Osun	2,118,883,555.68	2,655,049,761.21	2,738,102,673.38	2,869,627,687.71	10,381,663,677.98	Osun
Oyo	5,405,584,026.96	6,974,296,229.10	5,882,490,179.75	6,372,703,638.68	24,635,074,074.49	Oyo
Plateau	3,098,544,664.05	3,171,114,653.27	3,260,734,080.98	3,196,086,150.11	12,726,479,548.41	Plateau
Rivers	37,476,154,780.33	23,430,626,831.97	22,881,431,443.74	28,992,160,856.19	112,780,373,912.23	Rivers
Sokoto	2,178,862,395.60	3,471,332,012.60	7,758,924,708.94	5,352,889,902.91	18,762,009,020.05	Sokoto
Taraba	1,199,006,773.57	1,414,242,067.81	1,517,681,391.48	1,837,879,350.25	5,968,809,583.11	Taraba
Yobe	832,216,819.29	788,458,715.08	1,264,409,501.02	1,497,174,420.66	4,382,259,456.05	Yobe
Zamfara	1,314,770,380.33	1,342,423,061.06	1,795,550,065.48	3,753,952,085.27	8,206,695,592.14	Zamfara
FCT	20,081,794,991.21	15,156,199,846.47	14,023,986,002.58	16,257,682,814.56	65,519,663,654.82	FCT
TOTAL minus FCT	281,131,577,735.52	263,630,518,989.77	250,323,661,833.19	308,329,377,086.91	1,103,415,135,645.40	
TOTAL inc FCT	301,213,372,726.73	278,786,718,836.24	264,347,647,835.77	324,587,059,901.47	1,168,934,799,300.22	

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State Boards of
Internal Revenue

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